

Representing discourses as networks: potential applications of TheSu XML in network analysis for the history of ideas and science

Daniele Morrone [1]

1: KULeuven

Morrone Daniele. 2024. "Representing discourses as networks: potential applications of TheSu XML in network analysis for the history of ideas and science", *Historical Network Research 2024*, Lausanne, DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.12606611

This paper will discuss potential applications of the TheSu XML Annotation Schema in the history of ideas and science for purposes of network visualisation and analysis.

TheSu XML (Morrone 2023), "Thesis-Support", is an innovative tool for annotating declarative statements, or "theses", found in historical sources, like "the Earth revolves around the Sun" (Morrone 2022). Not limited to simple tagging of formal and thematic features of such claims, the model also allows linking the theses to their contextual "supports" (e.g., argumentative premises, explanatory remarks, introductions) and abstract "propositions" that broadly represent their content. By linking multiple theses to the same propositions, it is possible to connect identical or similar theses – along with their attached supports – within the same text or across different sources. The "Argumentative-Expository System" resulting from the annotation of all these interlinked elements forms a network that can be visualised and analysed.

The method is designed to aid in close reading of texts by revealing argumentative structures and rhetorical progressions, and to provide access to the contexts of claims to prevent misinterpretations. Representing the discourse conveyed in a text graphically as an argument map (cf. Stede and Schneider 2019, 36-43) can help understand the theses' interconnections, but challenges arise in optimising these maps for clarity and analyticity, especially when dealing with complex, densely interconnected discourses.

In contrast with argument map-like visualisations, whose effectiveness strictly depends on the number of their nodes and edges being sufficiently small, graphs intended for network analysis have the advantage of scalability, even providing greater insights with larger Argumentative-Expository Systems. Indeed, annotating claims concerning, for instance, the Earth's revolution around the Sun, and the reverse, across diverse sources over centuries may reveal patterns in claim co-occurrence, thematic clustering, roles in argumentation, and grounding in common or divergent demonstrations. Analysing such a network could uncover how frequently proponents of geocentrism engaged with heliocentric arguments, or how different astronomical arguments (based on observations, philosophical reasoning, or religious texts) were used to support opposing theories. All these patterns can potentially be used to identify historical trends or distinct traditions.

It is thus key to this paper's method to distinguish between two forms of automatic graph visualisation: one optimised for analyticity and close reading enhancement, and the other for quantitative network analysis, also at the potential expense of readability. Accordingly, the paper will discuss how to optimise the automatic treatment of TheSu XML data for generating both types of graphs.

In presenting a general overview of TheSu XML and its intended applications, the paper will draw on my experience annotating claims and arguments onto TEI XML editions of ancient philosophical-scientific texts (primarily from the collection Cerrato et al. 2019-2021). Building upon recent groundwork for ongoing historical research, it will focus on the chemistry of lead and lead white, with particular interest in how network analysis can reveal shifts in the understanding of their properties and applications across authors and time.

After showcasing annotation examples of ideas concerning lead and its white pigimentary product, the paper will discuss the design of a working Python script prototype for network conversion and graph representation of Argumentative-Expository Systems. This prototype uses the lxml library to convert

selected TheSu XML features into nodes, edges, and attributes of a directed graph in DOT format. The script generates two distinct outputs: first, a DOT document optimised for argument map visualisation through GraphViz, to enhance close reading and textual analysis of short passages or small combinations of these (see Figure 1); and second, a DOT document designed for import into Gephi to enable network analysis of larger datasets (see Figure 2).

Figure 1. Example of an automatically visualised TheSu XML small argument map (GraphViz)

Two ancient recipes for making lead white (psimythion), reported by Theophrastus (De lapidibus 55) and Dioscorides (De materia medica 5 88.1), are represented as 'THESES' nodes and analysed in their respective steps, in turn represented as subordinate nodes connected in a sequence. The two recipes are connected to an abstract 'PROPOSITION' node representing the content of Theophrastus's recipe for comparison purposes: each step of Theophrastus's and Dioscorides's recipe is thus connected to the step(s) matching it (either exactly or with specified differences) in the abstract recipe's sequence.

Theophrastus's recipe is also connected to its immediate context of enunciation, through the inclusion of 'SUPPORT' nodes in the network. The recipe is not presented in isolation: it is explicitly presented as a specification of the claim that "lead white comes about by technical means", in turn introduced by an analogy with the claim that "the four colours made by kyanos from itself come about by technical means".

Each of these nodes may theoretically be also connected to its context, as well as to abstract 'PROPOSITION' nodes for comparison with similar claims occurring in other points of the same text or in other texts. In the present case, the passages represented in the network do not include argumentation, but only exposition and contextualisation.

The purpose of this argument map visualisation is to facilitate the analysis and comparison of the two recipes in their contexts, enhancing the close reading of the passages in which they are embedded. It was created via a Python script through automatic conversion of selected features of a TheSu XML annotation of the

Katsaros, T., Ioannis Liritzis, and N. Laskaris. 2010. 'Identification of Theophrastus' Pigments Egyptios Kyanos and Psimythion from Archaeological Excavations. A Case Study'. *ArcheoSciences. Revue d'archéométrie*, no. 34 (April): 69–80. <https://doi.org/10.4000/archeosciences.2632>.

Morrone, Daniele. 2023. 'TheSu XML Schema Definition, Ns 1.0' (Version 1). KU Leuven RDR. <https://doi.org/10.48804/KD8QPO> .

Morrone, Daniele. 2022. 'Plutarch's Chemistry of Stones and Metals: Conceptions and Explanations. With an Appendix on the TheSu XML Annotation Scheme'. PhD Thesis, University of Bologna. <http://amsdottorato.unibo.it/10376/>.

Stede, Manfred, and Jodi Schneider. 2019. *Argumentation Mining*. San Rafael: Morgan & Claypool Publishers.

Acknowledgement

This paper is part of Jan Opsomer's research project Not Another History of Platonism: The Role of Aristotle's Criticisms of Plato in the Development of Ancient Platonism, acronym PlatoViaAristotle. The PlatoViaAristotle project has received funding from the European Research Council (ERC) under the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme (G.A. 885273).